

REVIEW OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. In this article, the modern methods of English language teaching, which are widely used today in higher educational institutions and non-state educational institutions of our republic, are identified. Also, fundamental, linguistic, sociocultural, communicative methods are comparatively analyzed, their role and importance in the educational process is discussed.

Keywords: English language, method, fundamental, linguistics, technology, communication, intensive, teaching.

INTRODUCTION

All people living on earth are not only witnesses of the rapidly changing world, but also direct participants in complex and continuous processes such as the development and progress of world culture and science and technology. At this point, learning English, which is one of the world's leading languages and has become the second language of communication for 40 percent of the world's population today, is of great importance [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In a short period of time, the state standards for the continuous education system in our country for foreign languages were developed, the requirements for the level of training of graduates of all stages of education were determined. The standards of the continuous education system of Uzbekistan were developed based on the requirements of the universally recognized Council of Europe "European Competences for Foreign Language Learning: Learning, Teaching and Assessment" (CEFR). In order to ensure that the state education standards are thorough in all aspects, a group of experts led by England's Rod Bolbaito and Davis Alan was involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the recent past, English language teaching focused mainly on grammar. A lot of time was devoted to reading and translating texts, and sometimes to memorizing "topics" and dictation to revive the sameness at least a little, and this process required painstaking work. Today, the main offer in the language market is formed according to the demand of the consumer. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, a mature specialist in linguistics and the methodology of teaching foreign languages, "Today, language teaching has become functional, and as a result of the strengthening of integration processes, the study of foreign

languages, in particular, English, has become more relevant. But the history of language or its theory is what modern language learners are concerned with.

Uzbekistan is not interested in foreign languages. English has become necessary for them to meet their life needs" [3]. Currently, there are several methods offered to students learning English. One of them is the **fundamental method**. It requires at least 2-3 years of study, deep study of grammar. This method is mainly used in the training of professional translators, and at the end of their studies, students will be able to look at the world through the eyes of a "native speaker". Based on it, language is studied as a real and complete means of communication.

Currently, the fundamental method has not changed its purpose, but many other methods have entered the field of competition with the fundamental method. One of them is the **linguo-sociocultural method**. This method requires learning the language in a social and cultural environment. Its supporters condemn the fact that students are made to study "dead" lexical-grammatical forms. According to them, "a person is a product of culture. So, the language too." In most cases, not learning the language in accordance with social life causes many mistakes. For example, a student of English might use the grammatically correct phrase "The Queen and Her relatives", but a British citizen would have difficulty understanding that "The Royal Family" is meant.

According to linguists, 52% of such cases are the direct transfer of expressions from the mother tongue into English, and 44% are determined by the insufficient capacity of the language learner. The most important thing in the process of learning a language is how accurate the information content is.

Linguistic and sociocultural method covers two types of communication. It is language and intercultural communication. A student of a higher education institution should not only acquire high levels of reading, writing and translation in English, but also learn to see English from the perspective of other people's culture. The English language teacher should pay attention to these aspects in the process of language teaching.

Today, this is effectively done by the 5-step "Headway" tutorial created by British designers John and Liz Soar. This textbook for learning English includes a complete methodological package, i.e. a textbook for students and a teacher, 120 hours of audio cassettes covering Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate, Upper-Intermediate. Each lesson in the textbook consists of several sections. The first covers speaking skills, while the second focuses on the formation of language skills (skills development). The next ones consist of

working on texts (scan reading, reading for gist, summary reading, etc.), questions and answers, listening to the audio tape and returning it.

Another very popular method of teaching English in today's fast-paced world is the **intensive method**. About 25 percent of it is based on clichés, that is, memorization of the most necessary phrases for communication. Of course, a student who chooses this method of language learning may not be able to read Byron's works in the original, but he can communicate with his interlocutor when necessary. The teacher teaching through this method mainly uses dialogues as a weapon. English in 2 weeks through the intensive method. It is not possible to learn foreign languages in Uzbekistan, but hardworking students who work on themselves can easily master the language in 3 months.

CONCLUSION

The use of these teaching methods in English classes allows the student to be an active participant in the process, to form and develop cognitive activity. In conclusion, whatever method the teacher chooses to teach English, it should be based on the desire to provide more knowledge to the student and help young people master the English language well. Only then will any method be effective.

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